

Quantum Entropy and Energy States

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Shannon's entropy: $-k \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ is expressed in terms of $P(i)$ the probability for state i . If entropy exists as a concept separated from the first law of thermodynamics with $dW=0$, then it is not clear what set of states i should be taken in quantum mechanics. In classical statistical mechanics, each particle is automatically described by its position and momentum vectors for no internal motion. For example a pure energy eigenstate wavefunction $W_n(x)$ may be written in terms of many different orthonormal mathematical basis sets e.g. $W_n(x) = \sum_i b_i \phi_i(x)$ with probabilities b_i^2 . Thus one may create many types of entropy expressions using Shannon's form without any other physical considerations.

For example, $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and one may create S_p which is usually done in the literature. In previous notes we have argued that $S_n = S_p(n) + S_x(n)$. For a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, $S_x(n) = S_x$. The sum of the two entropies ensures that the parameter L (box size) vanishes so that a quantum adiabatic transformation is isentropic. Thus a consideration other than Shannon's form has been used to obtain $S_n = S_p(n) + S_x$ for a particle in a box. Furthermore one may argue Shannon's form even for a pure state based on $S = S_1 + S_2$ where 1 and 2 represent two systems. A question still remains: Why are S_x and S_p entropies used and not some other set? Furthermore for a system with several energy levels e_i one might ask why $-\sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ is used as in (1)? In a previous note (2) we considered that Shannon's form of entropy follows from $dE = TdS$ ($dW=0$) with $dE = \sum_i e_i dP(e_i)$. Furthermore we argued that $P(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ is a solution, but so is $C(T) \exp(-e_i/T) \exp(S_i)$ where $S_i = S_{x,i} + S_{p,i}$ for the pure bound state. In other words, specific states related to the physical situation are chosen and entropy constructed from $dE = TdS$ to reflect this.

In this note we argue that entropy may be less related to counting arrangements than to considering the issues involved in energy transfers within a system.

Entropy in Terms of Maximum Number of Arrangements

If entropy is the \ln of the number of arrangements of a system, then it exists as a concept on its own. If on the other hand it is directly linked to the first law of thermodynamics, $dE = TdS - dW$, then it seems that physical considerations, related to the manner in which energy changes, enter.

Consider entropy as a concept linked to the number arrangements possible. In such a case there seems to be an ambiguity for quantum systems because Shannon's form is obtained from the high N limit of \ln factorial counts of arrangements. This may be applied to various sets of quantum probabilities. For example, given a quantum energy eigenstate $W(x)$ one may use any orthonormal basis $W(x) = \sum_i b_i \phi_i(x)$ and define $P(i) = b_i^2$ and create S (variable linked to i) = $-\sum_i b_i^2 \ln(b_i^2)$ as is done for the variable p =momentum. In such a case, which entropy does one use?

Entropy Linked to The First Law of Thermodynamics

If one considers entropy as linked to the first law of thermodynamics, then it seems matters are different. Consider a pure bound state with $W_n(x)$ as a solution of the Schrodinger equation. This is linked to a classical type of probability $P(x) = W_n(x)W_n(x)$. For $dW_{\text{work}}=0$, the first law of thermodynamics is $dE = TdS$. Given a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, the parameter $L = \text{box size}$ appears. In such a case, one must ask: What are the physical ways to change E (average energy)? Changing the box size is an immediate choice. Furthermore given that $E_n = n^2/L^2 \cdot \text{constant}$, one may consider a quantum adiabatic transformation in which L changes and n remains constant and associate this with dW_{work} i.e. $dQ=0$. If one wishes to create entropy from probabilities, what probability should be used? As in classical thermodynamics one may consider a probability related to x i.e. $P(x)$. In fact, given that energy in a bound state depends on average kinetic energy as well as $V(x)$ for the usual scenario, one might expect $P(x)P(p)$ to be the overall probability in question just as in the classical case even though the two statistical systems are very different. This, however, is not the same as classical physics because in the quantum scenario one does not simultaneously know x and p . Thus it seems that one would not want to link $S_x + S_p$ to physical arrangements.

$P(x)$ depends on $1/L$. If one wishes entropy to be linear i.e. $S = S_1 + S_2$ for two identical systems then a solution is $-P(x)\ln(P(x))$. This result depends on $\ln(L)$ so one needs a second entropy which gives $-\ln(L)$. If one uses entropy associated with a Fourier transform variable then one is guaranteed $P(\text{Fourier variable})$ is proportional to L . For the quantum case, p momentum is the Fourier variable associated with x and so $S_n = S_{x,n} + S_{p,n}$. Thus, considerations of the \ln of arrangements is not made. Rather one makes choices based on the first law of thermodynamics i.e. on an adiabatic transformation being isentropic. Using $S_x + S_p$ does not just work for the parameter L for a particle in a box, but for any parameter (e.g spring constant k) for which the Schrodinger equation may be written in terms of $y = bx$ with $E \rightarrow E/bb$, then $P(x)$ goes as $1/b$ and $P(p)$ as b so that $S_x + S_p$ eliminates b , the parameter.

It is interesting to note that in the quantum bound state world, one either knows p exactly or x exactly yet $P(x)P(p)$ is still used as the overall probability in Shannon's entropy. This suggests that one should perhaps not take the idea of entropy as $\ln\{\text{arrangements}\}$ too seriously, but rather seek a solution of $dE = TdS$ ($dW_{\text{work}}=0$) based on probabilities. In such a case, Shannon's form is an exact solution (not an approximation as in the case of $\ln\{\text{factorial expression yielding arrangements}\}$ which only applies in the limit of high N i.e. using Stirling's approximation). If this is the case, then one might not be worried about various orthonormal basis functions yielding different entropies. Rather one would be concerned about the physical way in which energy changes. This, however, is still a difficult problem as one may not know exactly how an energy level influences changes to and from it. For example, consider a system in which $e_3 - e_2 = A$ and $e_6 - e_5 = A/2$. It may not be the case that it is as easy to jump from e_2 to e_3 as it is to jump from e_5 to e_6 twice even though the energy changes are the same in both scenarios.

$$W(x,t) = \text{Sum over } n \text{ } a_n(t) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$$

A main purpose of the Schrodinger equation is to determine e_n values because $e_j e_i$ correspond to experimentally observable photons which may be emitted or absorbed depending

on whether j is greater than or less than i . Thus one may envision an equilibrium in which a particle absorbs and emits photons. In other words there is a physical manner in which e_n may change other than by increasing the size of a box with infinite potential walls. Thus,

$$E_{ave} = \sum_n a_n e_n \quad ((1))$$

which follows from the wavefunction $W(x,t) = \sum_n a_n(t) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$ and $\langle W|H|W \rangle$ and suggests that $P(E_n) = a_n$ may be the probability to use in calculating an entropy expression for the first law of thermodynamics $dE = TdS - dWork$. In fact, this is done in (1) i.e.

$$S/(-k) = \sum_n a_n \ln\{a_n\} \quad ((2))$$

. The first law only deals with changes in average energy and e_n values do not change.

One may ask: Why not use: $W(x,t)W(x,t) = P(x)$ and $P(p) = a(p,t)a(p,t)$ in a Shannon's entropy expression to obtain $S = S_x + S_p$ just as in the pure energy eigenstate case? This it seems would be a natural extension of the pure eigenstate case and the parameter L would disappear for the adiabatic scenario as $W_n(x)$ may be written as $1/\sqrt{L} W_n(x/L)$.

((1)) suggests that energy changes occur if the particle changes from one state to another by emitting or absorbing a photon. Thus, the idea of using e_n as a state seems reasonable because it is linked to physical photons. What may not be reasonable is to assume that $P(e_i) = P(e_i/T)$ only depends on a parameter T temperature. The form e_i/T is used because e_i is proportional to n/LL . For a quantum adiabatic transformation n stays constant, but L changes so if one has a T proportional to $1/LL$, then a_n remains unchanged and there is no entropy change as in the pure eigenstate case.

It may not, however, be the case that $P(e_i/T)$ depends only on the e_i value from state i . Given that one is interested in energy changes and that these occur through the absorption and emission of photons, the form $P(e_i/T) = C(T)\exp(-e_i/T)$ which is a solution of ((1)) and ((2)) for $dWork=0$ assumes that only energy e_i matters i.e a photon is absorbed or emitted just as easily from e_1 to e_2 as from e_1 to e_3 . This may not be the physical case.

If one considers a pure eigenstate for which $e_n = n/LL$ constant, one may make a quantum adiabatic change by changing L , keeping n constant. It seems a thermal change is linked to holding L constant and changing n , even though this would be an infinitesimal change only for n large. As n becomes large for a particle in a box $S_p(n) \rightarrow$ constant yet there is still a small n dependence. Thus it seems that pure state entropy could also have an effect on the change in energy. Thus one may consider a second solution to $dE = TdS$ ($dWork=0$) namely using $P(e_i/T)P_i(x)P_i(p)$ which yields:

$$S/(-k) = \sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i)) + \sum_i P(e_i)(S_p(i) + S_x) \quad ((3))$$

Particle in a box with infinite potential walls. In such a case:

$$P(e_i/T) = C(T)\exp(-e_i/T) \exp(S(i)) \text{ instead of } C(T)\exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((4))$$

In fact, $S(i)$ could be replaced by any function of i linked to the physical absorption or emission of photons. The reason $S(i)$ is used is because one wishes to have entropy become $S(1)$ if $P(e_i)=0$ if $i \neq 1$ and $P(e_1)=1$. In other words, one wishes to use quantum thermodynamics for a pure eigenstate (jumping to another) as well as for an mixed state of different eigenstates.

Using $dE=TdS+dWork$ and treating S as a function of probabilities is not necessarily based on strict counting of arrangements, but must represent the physics involved with changing from one energy state to another. The energy state e_i seems to be defined by the existence of absorbed and emitted photons, but there may be level i related physics (related to pure eigenstate $S=S_p+S_x$) which enhances or hinders absorption or emission at a particular i level. Thus we argue that e_i is not the only consideration in a problem involving $dE= \sum \text{over } e_i P(e_i)$ i.e. $E_{ave} = \sum \text{over } i e_i P(e_i/T, S_i=S_p(i)+S_x(i))$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if the definition of entropy stands by itself as $-k \ln \{\text{number of arrangements of a system}\}$ then in the quantum situation it may be difficult to determine how to count arrangements as one cannot characterize a particle by its position and momentum at an instant in time. One may write a wavefunction in terms of many orthonormal basis sets and use the coefficients squared as probabilities. This leads to many definitions of entropy.

We argue that entropy may need to be defined with respect to the first law of thermodynamics $dE=TdS - dWork$. The idea of using Shannon's form $-\sum \text{over } n P(e_n) \ln(P(e_n))$ allows for a linear situation i.e. $S=S_1+S_2$ just as in the case of classical thermodynamics. For $dWork=0$ $P(e_n)=C(T) \exp(-e_n/T)$ is a solution where T is needed to offset the $1/L$ dependence of e_n and allow a quantum adiabatic transformation to be isentropic i.e. $dP(e_n)=0$ as L changes for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. A more general solution of $P(e_n)$, however, is also possible as shown in (2) i.e. $P(e_n) = C(T) \exp(-e_n/T) \exp(S_n)$. In other words, e_n are believed to exist because of observed emitted and absorbed photons, but this absorption and emission may depend on the entropy of level n itself and not just on energy differences between levels. Thus entropy, as an idea, may not be so closely linked to the $\ln\{\text{arrangements}\}$, but rather to the details of how energy may change in a physical system. The fact that a quantum wavefunction may be written in terms of many different orthonormal basis series may not impact entropy as one may have to use a basis set which is linked to the physical way in which energy changes in the system (e.g. via photons etc), but also to incorporate S_x+S_p entropies of pure states if these are to be treated thermodynamically as well.

References

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